

OPTIMIZATION OF ADHESIVE BONDED JOINTS IN GRP PRESSURE PIPING

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ABSTRACT

Stress concentrations in grp pressure piping can be reduced using a tubular lap joint with an elastic inner-ring. Bending stresses arise in the area of the joint due to differential radial expansion of pipe and joint. The Tsai-Wu failure criteria coefficient for pipe and joint was comparable to that of a scarf joint, using a joint with an elastic inner-ring and a winding angle of 45 or 35°. Increasing the joint thickness reduced stress concentrations significantly. Benefits from using tubular lap-joints are better support during handling and assembly and easier machining of the pipe ends as compared to scarf joints.

INTRODUCTION

Glass-fibre reinforced plastic piping are increasingly being used in offshore installations, mainly in seawater systems. Featuring high corrosion resistance, low weight, low maintenance cost and faster and easier installation compared to steel pipes. Factors that have restricted more extensive use of these materials have been the concern about fire hazard and lack of documentation on structural behaviour and damage when exposed to offshore loadings. Offshore loadings include vibration from such diverse sources as seismic disturbances, vibrating machinery, wind loads or fluid transients. Fluid transients, or waterhammer, can reach magnitudes far higher than the design pressure, and it is a cyclic phenomenon that can cause fatigue damage as well as instantaneous failure.

A previous investigation[1] on the fatigue damage of grp piping subject to waterhammer revealed weak points in the pipe muff joints being used. Cracks penetrated the muff joints causing leakage, the pipe walls in the nearest proximity of the muff joint were also damaged. Although no leakage occurred through the pipe wall, weeping was detected in some of the tests. The results from the fatigue testing indicates that concern should be taken in the design of the joint to prevent failure of joint and pipe from bending stresses.

A grp pressure pipe is mostly designed to withstand hoop stresses twice as large as the axial stresses, the membrane stress situation. This is achieved using a winding angle of 55°. It can be shown that if a pipe is restricted in its radial deformation at its end by an infinitely stiff flange, the total axial

stresses close to the flange could become twice as large as the hoop stresses[2]. This should be taken into consideration when designing pipe joints for grp piping, which has the highest strength in the hoop direction.

A closed form solution for bonded joints of thin cylindrical shells is given by Terekova and Skoryi[3]. However the solution neglects the effect of adherend bending. A closed form solution for the axially loaded tubular lap joint is given by Lubkin and Reissner[4] and has been confirmed by Adams and Peppiatt[5] by using a finite element model with 8-node isoparametric elements.

The adhesive bonded tubular lap joint loaded in axial tension experiences stress concentrations due to three mechanisms[5]. When the same joint is loaded by internal pressure, giving membrane stresses as in a pressure vessel, the stress concentrations arise by an additional mechanism, adding further to the complexity. The mechanisms that give rise to the stress concentrations for the pressurized pipe joint are:

1. differential straining of the adherends
2. bending of the adherends due to their non-collinearity.
3. bending of the adherends due to differential radial displacement when pressurized
4. and end effects.

Common adhesives show a non-linear material behaviour. Thomsen[6] shows that by allowing for plastic deformation of the adhesive, the stress concentrations can be reduced in adhesive joints, and this effect is present even at low load levels.

The stress concentrations in an adhesive bonded joint can be reduced by several methods. An increase in the joint strength by 90-150 % can be achieved by a change in geometry or material properties of the joint ends[7]. Methods involved rounding of the adherend edges, different fillet shapes, reverse tapering and local denting of the adherend to reduce the stiffness.

The scarf joint is found to be stronger than the lap joint for most applications. The thickness transition reduces the stress concentration at the end of the joint. Unfortunately, in most applications, machining and handling pipes and joints with sharp scarf ends proves impractical. Also, when assembling pipes using scarf joints one has to apply a slight axial pressure to prevent the pipes from releasing before the adhesive is cured.

Adhesive fillets are shown to reduce stress concentrations when applied to the ends of the joint. By careful design, so as to reduce the risk of getting cracks in the fillet, the strength of a lap joint can be increased. An adhesive fillet at the end of a sharp edged joint seems likely to crack and lose its effect especially when exposed to cyclic loadings. Inside the pipe, an adhesive fillet with a crack could at its worst make the stress concentrations more severe. If pressurized water was allowed to penetrate into the crack it would increase the crack-opening forces and accelerate the crack growth.

The influence from bending stresses on the joint strength will be investigated. Investigations will be done to find out whether an increase in axial strength of the joint will reduce the hoop strength, resulting in a lower total strength of the joint. The Tsai-Wu failure criterion will be applied so as to better assess the total strength of the joint. For lap joints it is convenient with an axial stop to the pipe when inserted into the joint. The axial stop could be an inner-ring in the joint, with an inner-diameter equal to the pipe. By making the inner-ring of an elastic material this could act as an adhesive fillet.

GRP PIPE AND JOINTS

The pipe was an E-glass reinforced epoxy pipe of inner diameter, $d_i = 100$ mm, winding angle, $\alpha = 55^\circ$ and structural pipe wall thickness $t_p = 3.2$ mm. A basic muff joint is shown in Fig. 1. The geometrical layout of the joints were modified as shown in Fig. 2, which represents the circled area of Fig. 1. Two of the joints were tubular lap joints, A and B. The third joint, C, was a tubular scarf joint. One of the lap joints were modified by adding a flexible inner-ring made of the epoxy matrix. The length of the adhesive bond line, L , was 45 mm. The tip of the pipe scarf had a thickness of 0.5 mm, as it would be highly impractical to manufacture a sharper scarf joint tip. The tip of the joint scarf varied from 0.5 mm up to 6.9 mm depending on the joint thickness.

Figure 1: Basic layout of a muff joint coupling used in grp piping.

Figure 2: The three muff joint geometries used for analysis.

MATERIALS

The pipe and the joints were assumed to be made of the same E-glass and epoxy matrix system. The fibres had a modulus of elasticity of 72 GPa, a shear modulus of 30 MPa and a Poisson's ratio of 0.21. The epoxy had a modulus of elasticity of 3.2 GPa, a shear modulus of 1.2 GPa and a Poisson's ratio of 0.35. The fibre volume fraction was 55 %. The strength in tension was 2360 MPa for the fibre and 31 MPa for the epoxy matrix. The adhesive had the same properties as the epoxy matrix used for the grp. The pipe was made with a winding angle of 55° . The joints were made with the winding angle, α , equal to 35, 45 and 55° .

The material properties were calculated using elementary laminate theory for a $(+\alpha/-\alpha)$ laminate. The calculated values are listed in Table 1. The properties are defined in a cylindrical coordinate system where r is the radial direction, θ is the hoop direction and z is the axial direction of the pipe. E_i is the modulus of elasticity and G_{rz} is the shear modulus of the rz -plane. F_{ii}^T and F_{ii}^C is the strength of the laminate in tension and compression respectively. F_{rz}^{ss} is the shear strength in the rz -plane. The Poisson ratios, ν_{ij} refer to a column normalized stiffness matrix formulation.

Table 1: Properties for pipe and joint materials.

α	55°	45°	35°
E_r [GPa]	9.75	9.75	9.75
E_θ [GPa]	20.5	14.98	11.94
E_z [GPa]	12.00	14.98	20.5
G_{rz} [GPa]	3.43	3.75	4.12
$\nu_{r\theta}$	0.17	0.18	0.20
$\nu_{z\theta}$	0.56	0.47	0.33
ν_{rz}	0.20	0.18	0.17
F_r^T/F_r^C [MPa]	31 / 118	31 / 118	31 / 118
F_θ^T/F_θ^C [MPa]	183 / 205	94 / 178	55 / 153
F_z^T/F_z^C [MPa]	55 / 153	94 / 178	183 / 205
F_{rz}^{ss} [MPa]	17.2	18.7	20.6

FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

The pipe and joint were axisymmetric with respect to geometry and loading. Also, the joint was symmetric along the mid cross section of the joint. Taking these simplifications into account the problem could be reduced to a two degree of freedom per node model, using axisymmetric elements. The eight node isoparametric element was chosen for the finite element model, as this element represents large gradients of displacement better than the four node elements. As much as 60 elements were used in the axial direction of the adhesive bond line, with shorter elements at the end of the adhesive bond line than at the middle in a length ratio one to ten. Four elements were used in the thickness direction of the adhesive, six in the thickness direction of the pipe and from six to eighteen in the thickness direction of the joint, depending on the joint thickness. The meshing was done using quadratic elements only.

The load was applied as a pressure, $p_i = 1$ MPa, at the surface of the elements on the inside of the pipe and as an axial force at the end of the pipe, thereby representing the membrane stresses experienced by a pressure vessel consisting of a joint and pipes with capped ends. Symmetrical boundary conditions were applied to the nodes at the center cross-section of the joint, allowing radial- but no axial displacement.

The elements were given homogeneous and anisotropic material properties corresponding to Table 1. For evaluation a three dimensional version of the Tsai-Wu failure criterion[8] were applied to the joint and to the pipe. The stresses at the integration points of each element were extrapolated to the nodes and the failure criterion coefficient was calculated at each node. For the adhesive the stresses were assumed constant through the thickness. The stresses were reported at the center of the adhesive line.

RESULTS

Simulations were performed using three different joint types, all with three different fibre winding angles. The adhesive thickness were varied from 0.1 to 1.0 mm and the joint thickness from 3.2 to 9.6 mm. The adhesive stresses were normalized on the pipe inner-pressure, p_i , and plotted versus the distance from the end of the joint normalized on the length of the pipe-end inside the joint, z/L , Fig. 1 and 2.

INFLUENCE FROM THE JOINT THICKNESS

Fig. 3 shows the results from varying the thickness of joint A. Both the shear- and radial stresses were reduced with increasing joint thickness. The reduction was largest in the adhesive at the end of the pipe. At the same time, the maximum value of the Tsai-Wu failure coefficient was reduced from 0.69 to 0.28 for the joint and from 0.25 to 0.15 for the pipe.

Figure 3: Adhesive stresses depending on joint thickness; Joint A, $\alpha = 55^\circ$, $t_a = 0.2$ mm.

INFLUENCE FROM THE ADHESIVE THICKNESS

The adhesive stresses are reduced significantly when increasing the adhesive thickness from 0.1 mm to 0.5 mm. A further increase of the adhesive thickness reduces the stresses less abruptly. When looking at the pipe and the joint, the failure coefficient did not decrease as rapidly as did the adhesive stresses. The Tsai-Wu coefficient is reduced with some 15 % for the joint.

Figure 4: Adhesive stresses and Tsai-Wu coefficients in joint and pipe depending on adhesive thickness; Joint A, $\alpha = 55^\circ$, $t_j = 4.8$ mm.

INFLUENCE FROM THE JOINT TYPE AND WINDING ANGLE

By varying the winding angle in the joints the adhesive stresses were only slightly influenced. The maximum radial stresses and the maximum shear stresses for the adhesive are given in Table 2. The stresses are lowest for joint B and highest for joint C. Joint A shows high shear stresses but low radial stresses. The influence from the winding angle are accounting for a 15 % reduction in adhesive stresses at the most.

Table 2: Maximum shear- / radial stress in adhesive depending on joint type and winding angle. $t_j = 4.8$ mm, $t_a = 0.2$ mm.

α	Joint A	Joint B	Joint C
55°	-3.4 / 2.3	-2.6 / 1.77	-3.2 / 2.8
45°	-2.9 / 2.2	-2.8 / 2.0	-3.3 / 2.8
35°	-2.9 / 2.4	-2.7 / 2.0	-3.0 / 2.5

Table 3: Maximum Tsai-Wu failure criterion coefficient of joint / pipe depending on joint type and winding angle. $t_j = 4.8$ mm, $t_a = 0.2$ mm.

α	Joint A	Joint B	Joint C
55°	0.46 / 0.22	0.22 / 0.22	0.10 / 0.27
45°	0.34 / 0.25	0.14 / 0.24	0.12 / 0.28
35°	0.31 / 0.24	0.13 / 0.24	0.14 / 0.26

The Tsai-Wu coefficient for the joints are the lowest for joint C and the highest for joint A, Table 3. The Tsai-Wu coefficient of the pipe varies only slightly from joint to joint, but is highest for joint C. Joint A and B experiences a reduction of Tsai-Wu coefficient when reducing the joint winding angle from 55 to 45 or 35°.

CONCLUSION

The strength of joints for glass-fibre reinforced piping can be considerably improved by adopting simple modifications to a tubular lap joint. A tubular lap joint is far more practical during handling and machining as compared to a tubular scarf joint with its sharp edges.

Finite element calculations has been used to investigate the influence on joint strength and adhesive stresses from varying the joint type, the thickness of the joint, the thickness of the adhesive and the fibre winding angle of the joint.

By increasing the adhesive thickness the adhesive stresses were considerably reduced, while the Tsai-Wu failure coefficient for pipe and joint was less affected.

For the tubular lap joint, an increase in wall thickness from 3.2 to 9.6 mm gained a reduction in Tsai-Wu failure coefficient of 60 % for the joint and 40 % for the pipe.

In the area of the joint, the bending stresses due to differential radial expansion of the pipe and joint are significant. By aligning more of the fibres in the axial direction, the strength of the joint is increased. A reduction of joint winding angle from 55 to 45 or 35°, reduces the Tsai-Wu coefficient

of the tubular lap joint from 0.46 to 0.31, without changing the failure coefficient for the pipe. The adhesive stresses is reduced by 15 % at the most.

A modification was done to the tubular lap joint by incorporating a flexible inner-ring of the same material as the matrix. An inner-ring provides support to the pipe end during assembly and curing. Furthermore it acts as an elastic fillet, which is proven by several investigators to reduce stress concentrations at the end of the joint. When using a joint with an elastic inner-ring and a fibre winding angle of 35 or 45°, the failure coefficient of the joint and pipe was reduced to the same level as that of the scarf joint with the same wall thickness.

By small changes in geometry or fibre lay-up a significant increase of joint strength can be achieved. This could reduce the mean time between failure of grp-piping. Savings in maintenance cost and lost profit would be substantial.

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